

1 **Tle2 functions in embryonic stem cell fate choice during endoderm lineage specification.**

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7 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
8 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
9 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
10 describe a requirement for Tle2 in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo sapiens*.

11 Citations

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1. Roth, M., Bonev, B., Lindsay, J., Lea, R., Panagiotaki, N., Houart, C. and Papalopulu, N., 2010.
FoxG1 and TLE2 act cooperatively to regulate ventral telencephalon formation. *Development*, 137(9),
pp.1553-1562.